

ADJECTIVES AND SUBSTANTIVIZATION OF ADJECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the problems of the process of substantivation of adjectives in Modern English. The study of functions of adjectives and the process of substantivation provided in the literature on this theme is analyzed in the article.

Key words: *nationality, noun, adjective, verb, predicative, term, function, basic, conversion*

We have chosen this theme because we like adjectives from our early school age. It was interesting for us to investigate adjectives and to find something new that we didn't know before. First of all we found out the basic definitions of adjectives to describe it as part of speech. We used many theoretical books to do our course work, such as: « Modern English language» (Theoretical course grammar) V.N. Zhigadlo, I.P. Ivanova, L.L. Iofik. Moscow, 1956 y., Baker, Mark. 2005. Lexical Categories - Verbs, nouns and adjectives. Cambridge University Press, etc. Then we looked through the "Warren, Beatrice. (1984). Classifying adjectives. Gothenburg studies in English" to know their theories and thoughts about adjectives as a part of speech. Here what we found about it:

In grammar, an **adjective** is a part of speech that modifies a noun or a pronoun, usually by describing it or making its meaning more specific. Adjectives exist in most languages. The most widely recognized adjectives in English are words such as *big*, *old*, and *tired* that actually describe people, places, or things. These words can themselves be modified with adverbs, as in the phrase *very big*. The

articles *a*, *an*, and *the* and possessive nouns, such as *Mary's*, are classified as adjectives by some grammarians; however, such classification may be specific to one particular language. Other grammarians call such noun modifiers determiners. Similarly, possessive adjectives, such as *his* or *her*, are sometimes called determinative possessive pronouns, and demonstrative adjectives, such as *this* or *that*, are called determinative demonstratives. In some languages, participles are used as adjectives. Examples of participles used as adjectives are *lingering* in the phrase *lingering headache* and *broken* in the phrase *broken toys*. Nouns that modify other nouns are sometimes called modifying nouns, nouns used adjectivally, or just part of a compound noun (like the word *ice* in *ice cream*).

Adjectives.

According to the theories of Dixon, R. M. W. (1977). "Where have all the adjectives gone?" *Studies in Language*, 1, 19-80 :

Adjectives are the third major class of words in English, after nouns and verbs. Adjectives are words expressing properties of objects (e.g. large, blue, simple, clever, economic, progressive, productive, etc) and, hence, qualifying nouns. Adjectives in English do not change for number or case. The only grammatical category they have is the degrees of comparison. They are also characterized by functions in the sentence.

Substantivization of Adjectives.

Sometimes adjectives become substantivized. In this case they have the functions of nouns in the sentence and are always preceded by the definite article. Substantivized adjectives may have two meanings:

1) They may indicate a class of persons in a general sense (e.g. the poor = poor people, the dead = dead people, etc.) Such adjectives are plural in meaning and take a plural verb. e.g. The old receive pensions.

The young are always romantic, aren't they?

The blind are taught trades in special schools.

If we wish to denote a single person we must add a noun. e.g. The old man receives a pension. If we wish to refer to a particular group of persons (not the whole class), it

is also necessary to add a noun. e.g. The young are usually intolerant. The young men are fishing. Some adjectives denoting nationalities (e.g. English, French, Dutch) are used in the same way.

e.g. The English are great lovers of tea. There were a few English people among the tourists.

2) Substantivized adjectives may also indicate an abstract notion. Then they are singular in meaning and take a singular verb.

e.g. The good in him outweighs the bad.

My mother never lost her taste for extravagant.

Syntactic Functions of Adjectives.

Adjectives may serve in the sentence as:

1) an attribute e.g. Do you see the small green boat, which has such an odd shape?
The lights of the farm blazed out in the windy darkness.

Adjectives used as attributes usually immediately precede the noun.

Normally there is no pause between the adjective and the noun. Such attributes are called close attributes. However, an adjective placed in pre-position to the noun may be separated from it by a pause. Then it becomes a loose attribute. e.g. Clever and tactful, George listened to my story with deep concern.

Yet loose attributes are more often found in post-position to the noun.

e.g. My father, happy and tired, kissed me good-night.

2) a predicative e.g. Her smile was almost professional. He looked mature, sober and calm. 3) part of a compound verbal predicate e.g. He stood silent, with his back turned to the window. She lay motionless, as if she were asleep.

4) an objective predicative e.g. I thought him very intelligent.

She wore her hair short. 5) a subjective predicative e.g. The door was closed tight.
Her hair was dyed blonde.

It should be noted that most adjectives can be used both attributively and predicatively, but some, among them those beginning with a-, can be used only as predicative (e.g. afraid, asleep, along, alive, awake, ashamed and also content, sorry,

well, ill, due, etc.) A few adjectives can be used only as attributes (e.g. outer, major, minor, only, whole, former, latter and some others).

The subject of our investigation was adjectives. What we have learnt about adjectives is that most English adjectives have comparative and superlative forms. These are generally constructed in one of two ways: either by suffixes (*big, bigger, biggest*) or by the use of the grammatical particles *more* and *most*. We have investigated that some adjectives have suppletive forms in their comparison, such as *good, better, best*. Comparative and superlative forms apply only to the base form of the adjective, so that duplicate forms like *most biggest* or *worser* are nonstandard (although *lesser* is sometimes permitted as a variant of *less*). A few adjectives have no comparative but a superlative with *-most*: *uppermost, westernmost*, etc. Also it has its own degrees, such as comparison, etc. Those such as *male, female, extant* and *extinct* which express "absolute" qualities do not admit comparisons: one animal cannot be more extinct than another. Similarly in *a planktonic organism* the adjective *planktonic* simply means plankton-type; there are no degrees or grades of planktonic. Other cases are more debatable. Grammatical prescriptivists frequently object to phrases such as *more perfect* on the grounds that something either is perfect or it is not. However, many speakers of English accept the phrase as meaning *more nearly perfect*. An adjective that causes particular controversy in this respect is *unique*. The formulations *more unique* and *most unique* are guaranteed to raise the hackles of purists. Which English adjectives are compared by *-er/-est* and which by *more/most* is a complex matter of English idiom. Generally, shorter adjectives (including most monosyllabic adjectives), Anglo-Saxon words, and shorter, fully domesticated French words (e.g. *noble*) use the suffixes *-er/-est*. Adjectives with two syllables vary. Some take either form, and the situation determines the usage. For example, one will see *commoner* and *more common*, depending on which sounds better in the context. Two-syllable adjectives that end in the sound [i], most often spelled with y, generally take *-er/-est*, e.g., *pretty : prettier : prettiest*. It was pleasant to investigate adjectives and we think that it is not the end of its investigation. We will

continue this theme on our diploma work. Thank you for spending time on reading our course work!

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